

CREEP OF FIBER-REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

J.-M. Yang, R. B. Thayer, S. T. Chen and W. Lin
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
University of California
Los Angeles, CA 90024-1595

ABSTRACT

The creep response of the SCS-6 fiber-reinforced Si_3N_4 and Nicalon fiber-reinforced SiC composites has been measured using four-point flexural loading at temperatures between 1100- 1450 °C and at stress levels ranging from 60 to 350 MPa. Parameters characterizing the stress and temperature dependence of steady-state creep rates were determined. Mechanisms of creep deformation and damage were also investigated. The results indicate that the creep resistance of ceramics can be significantly improved through the addition of continuous fibers.

KEYWORDS: Creep, Ceramic-Matrix Composites, Silicon Carbide, Silicon Nitride

1.INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber-reinforced ceramic matrix composites are promising engineering materials for high temperature structural applications such as gas turbine engines [1]. However, before these composites can be used reliably in structural applications at elevated-temperatures, a thorough understanding of their creep characteristics and the mechanisms controlling creep under these severe condition must be developed. Creep of composite can result in severe microstructural damage in the form of fiber breakage, matrix cracking and interfacial debonding that reduce the load-bearing capability and eventually cause component failure. Up-to-now, only a limited work has been conducted to address the problem of high-temperature creep deformation in ceramic composites with continuous fibers [2,3]. A fundamental understanding of time-dependent deformation at elevated-temperatures is needed for further improvements in the mechanical and environmental reliability of these materials.

This work is conducted to characterize the creep behavior of the SCS-6 fiber-reinforced Si₃N₄ and Nicalon fiber-reinforced SiC composites at elevated-temperatures. The creep responses at various temperatures and stresses as well as the kinetics of creep deformation were measured. The role of microstructural parameters on the mechanisms of creep deformation and damage was also determined.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Composites used in this study consisted of an unidirectional and a [0/90] cross-ply SCS-6/Si₃N₄ composite and a 2-D plain-weave Nicalon/SiC composite. The unidirectional and cross-ply Si₃N₄ composites with 20 v/o fiber loading were prepared via a pre-preg tape lay-up technique. The composite preforms were then consolidated by hot-pressing at 1700 °C and 70 MPa for 1 hour in a N₂ atmosphere. To facilitate matrix densification, sintering additives of 5.0 wt. % Y₂O₃ and 1.25 wt. % MgO were added to the starting Si₃N₄ powder. A detailed description of the fabrication process can be found in References 4 and 5. The Nicalon/SiC composite was fabricated by a chemical vapor infiltration technique. The fiber volume fraction is 35 % with matrix porosity of approximately 15 %. Bars were sectioned from composite plates and ground to dimensions of approximately 3 x 4 x 50 mm, then polished to a 6 mm finish. Edges were chamfered to 45°.

The creep testing was conducted in air at temperatures of 1100 to 1450 °C and at stresses ranging from 60 to 350 MPa. Specimens were loaded in four-point bending fixture of hot-pressed SiC with inner and outer span of 20 and 40 mm, respectively. Constant load was applied using a level system and a dead weight acting on the upper push rod. Load-point to center-point deflections were measured directly using a three probe spring-loaded LVDT scheme. Maximum outer fiber strains were calculated directly from the displacement measurements using the procedure described by Hollenberg [6]. To determine the kinetics of creep deformation, the following relationship was used: $\dot{\epsilon} = A \sigma^n \exp(-Q/RT)$, where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is steady state creep rate, A is the pre-exponential parameter which takes into account the microstructure and temperature effect, σ the applied stress level, n the stress exponent, Q the apparent activation energy and T the absolute temperature. After testing, the specimens were polished and examined using optical and scanning electron microscopy to characterize the creep deformation mechanisms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Unidirectional SCS-6/Si₃N₄ Composite

The creep response of the Si₃N₄ reinforced with 20 v/o SCS-6 fibers as a function of applied stress and temperature are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Inspection of these creep curves revealed that the composites exhibited primary creep during early stage of loading followed

by transition to a secondary or steady-state creep stage. Also, depending on the test conditions and test duration, some specimens exhibited tertiary creep eventually leading to rupture. The results indicate that the composite exhibited an excellent resistance to creep in flexure under the stresses employed in this study. For an increase of applied stress from 250 to 350 MPa, only a slight increase in steady-state creep rate was observed. However, the creep response of the composite is sensitive to temperature change. Figure 2 indicates that the strain-rate increases almost 3 orders of magnitude as the temperature increases from 1200 to 1425 °C.

Figure 3 is a plot of creep strain versus time curves for the monolithic Si_3N_4 deformed at 1200 °C for a range of stresses. The strain-rate is observed to increase almost two orders of magnitude as the applied stress increases from 68 to 185 MPa. Figure 4 is the strain versus time plot for monolithic Si_3N_4 at an applied stress of 100 MPa and temperatures from 1200 to 1350 °C. As the test temperature increases from 1200 to 1350 °C, the strain-rate is again observed to increase about two orders of magnitude.

Comparisons of the creep response between the monolithic and composite Si_3N_4 may be made in several areas. The most significant is the steady-state creep rate. For a 20 v/o composite having an applied load of 250 MPa, the stress in the matrix is 185 MPa (calculated from the isostrain rule-of-mixtures) which is the highest stress applied to the monolithic material. However, the steady-state creep rate of the composite is two orders of magnitude slower. In addition, the time required to attain a certain strain increases

Fig. 1 Creep response of the 20 v/o unidirectional SCS-6/ Si_3N_4 composite at 250 MPa and temperatures from 1200 to 1400 °C.

Fig. 2 Creep response of the 20 v/o unidirectional SCS-6/Si₃N₄ composite at 1200 °C and stresses from 250 to 350 MPa.

dramatically even at the higher stresses applied to the composite. Also the maximum strain induced after 150 hours at 350 MPa did not exceed 1.0%. These results clearly show that the creep resistance of the composite is far superior to that of the unreinforced matrix.

The apparent activation energies for the creep deformation processes were determined by plotting the steady-state creep rates against reciprocal temperature as shown in Fig. 5. Monolithic Si₃N₄ was tested at a constant stress of 100 MPa and temperatures from 1200 to 1350 °C, for which an apparent activation energy of 530 KJ/mol was calculated from a linear regression of the data. The 20 v/o composite, tested at 250 MPa and temperatures between 1200 and 1350 °C, exhibited an activation energy of 390 KJ/mol. However, at temperatures between 1350 to 1425 °C, the composite exhibited an activation energy of 1340 KJ/mole. The sharp increase in activation energy may be correlated to the melting of the free silicon deposits at the SiC grain boundaries which will lead to a substantial reduction of creep resistance in the fiber [7].

Figure 6 is steady-state creep rates of the composites and the unreinforced matrix plotted against the applied stress in log-log scale at 1200 °C. The linear regression analysis of creep rate/stress curves yields the stress exponent, n , which may be used to gain insight of the predominant mechanisms governing the creep behavior. The monolithic Si₃N₄ displayed a bi-linear stress dependence the stress exponent is 1.12 and 7.87 for applied stresses below and above 128 MPa, respectively. Based upon the above kinetic data and microstructural analysis, the deformation mechanisms of the unreinforced matrix was found to occur via grain boundary sliding, void growth and coalescence. The stress exponent of the composite is found to be 2.5 indicating that the rate-controlling mechanisms is different.

Fig. 3 Creep response of the monolithic Si_3N_4 at 1200°C and stresses from 68 to 185 MPa.

Fig. 4 Creep response of the monolithic Si_3N_4 at 100 MPa and temperatures from 1200 to 1350°C .

Fig. 5 Steady-state creep rates of the 20 v/o unidirectional SCS-6/ Si_3N_4 composite plotted against temperature.

Fig. 6 Steady-state creep rate of the 20 v/o unidirectional SCS-6/Si₃N₄ composite plotted against the applied stress at 1200 °C.

In order to examine the role of the fiber on the creep response of the composite, creep curves of the composite, the matrix and the fiber were plotted together in Fig. 7. Creep curve for the fiber was generated from the data reported by Dicarlo [7]. Inspection of Fig. 7 revealed that the initial composite creep response was dominated by the matrix, followed by a transition to a response dominated by the reinforcing fibers. This transitional response of the composite suggests substantial stress relaxation in the matrix due to a restraining force of the reinforcing fibers. Because of these restraining force supplied by the reinforcing fibers, the stresses in the matrix would not reach a level within the microcracking mechanism regime which operates in the monolithic Si₃N₄. However, the load transfer from the matrix results in very high stress in the fiber causing random fiber rupture. Fig. 8 is a representative tensile zone microstructure of the composite at steady state. Extensive fiber rupture without matrix cracking was clearly shown in this micrograph indicating the formation and growth of matrix crack was suppressed. At the fiber rupture sites, the load released by the fiber is transferred back to the matrix which sustains further creep deformation. Creep deformation of the matrix continues, resulting in local stress redistribution, until intact fiber segments adjacent to or further along the ruptured fiber supply a restraining force that allow the stresses in the matrix to relax again. A steady-state creep stage will be reached when an equilibrium is established between the rate of load transfer between the fiber and matrix and subsequent fiber rupture. This would result in multiple fiber fracture as shown in Fig. 8. A detailed discussion of the creep behavior of the composite can be found in reference 2.

Fig. 7 Creep strain versus time curves for the unreinforced matrix at stresses of 185 MPa, the SCS-6 fiber at stresses of 64 MPa, and for composite at an initial stress of 250 MPa.

Fig. 8 The tensile zone microstructure of the 20 v/o unidirectional SCS-6/Si₃N₄ composite at steady-state creep stage.

3.2. [0/90] Cross-ply SCS-6/Si₃N₄ Composite

Fig. 9 shows the creep response of the [0/90] cross-ply SCS-6/Si₃N₄ composite tested at 1200 °C and 200 MPa. The steady-state creep rate is again much lower than that of the unreinforced matrix at the same stress level. However, due to the distribution of fibers, the creep resistance of the [0/90] cross-ply composite at high applied stresses is less than that of the unidirectional composite. Microstructural analysis revealed matrix cracking did not occur -- this is also the case in the unidirectional composite. Meanwhile, multiple fiber fracture occurred in both the [0°] and [90°] laminae as shown in Fig. 10. The multiple fiber rupture in [90°] lamina could be caused by the normal and/or shear stresses which were generated due to the mismatch in Poisson's ratio between the [0°] and [90°] laminae during creep loading.

Fig. 9 Creep response of the 20 v/o [0/90] cross-ply SCS-6/Si₃N₄ composite at 200 MPa and 1200°C.

Fig. 10 Fiber fracture in the [90°] lamina

3.3. 2-D Nicalon/SiC Composites

The creep response of the SiC composite reinforced with 2-D plain-weave Nicalon fibers as a function of applied stresses and temperatures are shown in Figs. 11 and 12. Most of the specimens were tested to failure at fairly low fracture strain. Inspection of these curves shows that the creep strain of the composite increases with applied stress at a constant temperature, and similarly, increases with temperature at a constant stress. These curves also indicate that a well-developed steady-state creep stage is achieved in most of the

Fig. 11 Creep response of the 2-D Nicalon/SiC composite at 1300 °C and stresses from 90 to 125 MPa.

Fig. 12 Creep response of the 2-D Nicalon/SiC composite at 100 MPa and temperatures from 1200 to 1400 °C.

specimens under the current testing conditions. Fig. 13 is a plot of the steady-state creep rate versus the applied stress in a log-log scale. The stress exponent calculated from the slope of the curve was found to be about 5 at 1300 °C. The activation energy calculated from the plot of steady-state creep rates versus the absolute temperature at a constant stress of 100 MPa was found to be 477 KJ/mole. A preliminary examination of the fracture surface indicated that the composite exhibited brittle fracture behavior without significant fiber pullout.

Fig. 13 Steady-state creep rate of the 2-D Nicalon/SiC composite composite plotted against the applied stress at 1300 °C.

The kinetic data obtained in this investigation was compared with those of the fiber and matrix reported in the literature. The activation energy of a chemical-vapor-deposited-SiC was reported to be 174 ± 4.8 KJ/mole. The stress exponent under compressive stresses of 110 - 220 MPa was found to be between 2.3 to 3.7 at temperatures of 1550 - 1650 °C [8]. The major creep mechanism was identified as dislocation glide controlled by the energy of the Peierls stress hills. The activation energy and stress exponent of the Nicalon fiber was reported to be 370 - 490 KJ/mole and 1.1, respectively, at temperatures of 1100 - 1300 °C [9]. Diffusion and slippage of the microcrystalline SiC grains were the creep mechanisms identified. Furthermore, significant structural evolution and strength degradation of the fiber also occurred during creep testing at elevated-temperatures. Comparing the steady-state creep rates with the monolithic SiC reported in reference 8 revealed that the creep rate in the Nicalon/SiC composite is about one order of magnitude lower. Also, the activation energy of the composite is close to that of the fiber. It appears that the creep of the CVI-processed Nicalon/SiC composite is dominated by the Nicalon fiber. A detailed microstructural analysis is underway to further elucidate the creep mechanisms and to assess the effect of fiber structure and matrix porosity on creep resistance.

SUMMARY

The addition of SiC fibers into Si₃N₄ has resulted in a substantial improvement of creep resistance. Mechanisms of creep deformation were found to change from subcritical crack growth in the unreinforced matrix to repetitive matrix stress relaxation/fiber rupture/load transfer through the matrix. The creep response of the 2-D Nicalon/SiC composite has also been characterized. The creep rate in the composite is also lower than that of the matrix.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was partially supported by National Science Foundation (MSM 8809790 and MSS 9057030)

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